

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D9.5

Business and Exploitation Plan – v1

March 2022

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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Authors	George Stravodimos (HOLISTIC)
Contributors	-
Reviewers	ENG, NIA

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This report presents the exploitation plan that the entire consortium of the MES-CoBraD project will follow to sustain the outcomes beyond the end of the project, and the sustainability plan that paves the way for MES-CoBraD vision to maximise its expected impact. The MES-CoBraD solution and platform are the main project outcomes, and the Business plan is developed for its future commercialisation by the partners who are interested in. This is the first draft of the 'Business and Exploitation Plan' report.

Overall, MES-CoBraD will produce four (4) basic exploitation outcomes including the project platform that will be deployed at the pilots. Those four outcomes are:

- a) Respecting wellbeing promotion while minimizing harm,
- b) Sharing appropriately Real-World data in secure transparent and reliable way,
- c) Curtailing bias in decision making and ensuring that responsibility and accountability remains human- and hospital-centred, and
- d) Stimulating stakeholders to follow international codes of medical ethics and of practices for artificial intelligence.

The MES-CoBraD outcomes will be exploited by the different partner organisations, in Health provision Organisations, Patients (end-users) and Academia. Each organisation will exploit different outcomes because of their different nature. To do so, with regard to exploitation plan of the MES-CoBraD platform by stakeholders, the results of the project will inform health authorities more accurately of the healthcare needs of people with CoBraD diseases, their social barriers to healthcare access and compliance, as well as the real-world efficiency and safety of approved therapies. The exploitation of the MES-CoBraD platform can serve as a plan for developing comprehensive RWD registries for Clinical Trials beyond CoBraD and allow more accurate real-time assessments of health population authorities.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE & SCOPE

This report is the initial version of the Deliverable Business and Exploitation plan that will be updated annually and presents the planning of the exploitation and sustainability of the project's result on the basis of the pre-marketing activities. In this context, this report aims to:

- › Involve in setting up the environment for commercialising the MES-CoBraD solution and further exploit the outcomes.
- › Identify all the exploitable assets of the project, along with the results to be sustained following the end of the project.
- › Specify a plan for exploiting each one of the various assets, including exploitation of the asset by individual partners (where applicable) and joint exploitation.
- › Elaborate the plan including identification of the target market(s), identification of interested customers and stakeholders, market analysis, as well as exploitation modalities.

Finally, the key outcome of the project, the MES-CoBraD platform and its individual components will be implemented and deployed in pilot conditions. Therefore, the upcoming versions of this report will focus on the elaboration of the business model and the business plan to improve the commercialization of the project.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The first section of the present report introduces the content and the overall scope. The second section presents the overall exploitation plan and the project outcomes with their basic characteristics. The third section defines the business cases for the different target groups and the approach of the business model that the consortium members will develop. Finally, the fourth section presents the sustainability plan and the specific methodology that will take place during the project life cycle.

2 EXPLOITATION OUTCOMES

In this section, we describe in detail the MES-CoBraD key exploitable outcomes that this exploitation and sustainability plan is focused on. Exploitable outcomes will be updated in this section in future versions of this deliverable. The key exploitable outcomes of the MES-CoBraD project are the following:

2.1 MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

2.1.1 DESCRIPTION

MES-CoBraD major exploitable technical outcome is the MES-CoBraD Platform as a dynamic multidimensional modular platform that enhances the cyber protection of the healthcare ecosystem and ensures the patients’ data privacy and integrity, while providing tools for data visualization, analysis, and interpretation. The MES-CoBraD platform offers security and users will equitably have access to the entire database depending on their license. The platform will give access according to the validation and acceptance of the controller depending on the settings.

The MES-CoBraD platform will not only offer solutions and models, but also anonymized and depersonalized open data, according to the user’s license. There will be two types of quality products to be exploited, the first one is modules which are Open Source, and to which the user can integrate their multidimensional data. The second one is the uploading of data into the Platform’s datalake; in this module, the key element is on deciding by the settings how data will be included in the Platform.

Figure 1: MES-CoBraD platform architecture

The services that the MES-CoBraD platform gives to the users, are easily adapted, or embedded to existing, medical, clinical or health available infrastructures. The MES-CoBraD platform further embeds an innovative architecture to improve early diagnosis, provide more accurate prognosis, and identify optimal therapies in Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as represented in neurocognitive (dementia), seizure and sleep disorders. The MES-CoBraD platform aims at a society where patients and caregivers have the opportunity for the best possible quality of life irrespective of their health and socioeconomic background.

MES-CoBraD cutting-edge technology is expected to:

- › Improve clinical prognosis using supervised and unsupervised advanced analytics artificial intelligence models,
- › Enhance the platform with the use of Real-World Data.
- › Build a certified and trust platform through advanced usable transparency tools derived from health and care personnel.

2.1.2 EXPLOITATION GOALS

In this section, we present a summary of the main exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD Platform and the actions needed to fulfill these objectives.

Table 1: Exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD platform

Exploitation Goal	Actions Needed
Verify the business potential of the MES-CoBraD platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Develop the MES-CoBraD business model plan. › Receive feedback from the pilot use cases regarding the sustainability and exploitation potential of the platform. › Disseminate the MES-CoBraD platform and its value to a wide target audience (customers, and stakeholders).

2.2 MES-COBRA D PILOT USE CASES

Four inter-related Pilot Uses Cases (PUC) will be pursued to advance scientific knowledge in CoBraD, serve as examples of the exploitation potential of the MES-CoBraD Platform, maximizing novelty and impact, and highlighting the platform’s integration potential of multisource RWD for diverse clinical-research projects in CoBraD through its abstract methodology. Each PUC will address clinical, research, and technological challenges faced in medicine, and especially in CoBraD and each PUC is an indicative case of the MES-CoBraD project’s Expected Impact, as called for by the Work Program.

2.2.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOTS

Table 2: MES-CoBraD pilot activities

Pilots	Description
PUC 1: MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol	Is a representative case of how the MES-CoBraD Platform will integrate RWD, addressing several of the clinical, research and technological challenges and the expected impact that the work programme calls for.
PUC 2: MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication	Highlights the potential of MES-CoBraD Platform in advancing the precision medicine through advances analytic modules.
PUC3: MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication	Assesses the MES-CoBraD Platform cross-sectionally and longitudinally in assessing clinical

Reassessment	outcomes in relation to established therapies in real-world practice.
PUC4: Development and Validation of a Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders – MES-CoBraD	Focuses on the development of the Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment and Management of CoBraD and its cross-validation throughout the project’s lifetime.

Detailed description of the pilot activities is included in “D8.2: MES-CoBraD Validation Framework.” The exploitation of the pilot use cases is a key process of the project because will record the deployment of the platform.

2.3 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

2.3.1 DESCRIPTION

MES-CoBraD research and development activities will result to policy recommendations and best practices that should be exploited by the key policy makers and stakeholders. In the project, the Work Package 4 allows for identifying policy recommendations and the Work Package 9 is responsible for disseminating them. The exploitation plan will focus on identifying key policies that should be promoted and disseminated to the key policy makers and stakeholders.

2.3.2 EXPLOITATION GOALS

In this section the aim is to develop a policy recommendation and support dialogue with the policy makers and the stakeholders at the EU and at national level, aiming at increasing the policy investments to the platform and the cyber protection of the Real-World data.

Table 3 : Exploitation objectives for MES-CoBraD policy recommendations

Exploitation Goal	Actions Needed
Policy Recommendations and Support dialogue with the policy makers and the stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Develop policy recommendations, best practices based on the outcomes of the MES-CoBraD project, especially on the outcomes of the pilot use cases.

2.4 SCIENTIFIC & TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

2.4.1 DESCRIPTION

As already presented in the deliverable “D1.2: Scientific, Technical and Innovation Roadmap”, one of the main goals of the MES-CoBraD project is to create a scientific and innovation roadmap that provides steps that are necessary to achieve the MES-CoBraD scope, vision and guidelines to provide help to healthcare providers, industry, companies, hospitals and scientists who can improve the patient’s life, innovation and competitiveness. The scientific roadmap focuses on the necessary steps for realizing the optimum use of RWD, techniques, services, toolkits and methodologies of the MES-CoBraD Platform. In order for MES-CoBraD to realise successfully its vision within a scientific and social framework, a set of objectives are set throughout its duration as well as the exploitation of the project’s results after its end. The overall project success will be defined by the efficiency and effectiveness of the appropriate synthesis, as well as the individual quality of the specific achievements related to the project’s objectives, clearly measured

by key performance indicators. Scientific and Societal Objectives will be pursued in tandem with Technological Objectives (see respective chapter) to maximise impact and chance of success. Scientific and social objectives have the following traits:

- › **Scientific objectives** focus on the scientific work that will be pursued to deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles.
- › **Societal objectives** focus on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the gained spread of the excellence, the expansion of its ecosystem, and the real-life sustainability.

In the table below, the Exploitation goals of MES-CoBraD project are presented:

Table 4: Exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD scientific, technical and educational knowledge

Exploitation Goal	Actions Needed
New and improved scientific, technical, and educational knowledge	Three educational infrastructures to be improved (NTUA, Uppsala, University of Edinburgh).
Attaching added value to on-going innovation, providing demonstrators built during the MES-CoBraD project implementation to engage public administrations, bringing pioneer ideas and knowledge to university students that will impact their academic work (PhD dissertation, post-Doc, papers, etc.) along with the practical experience obtained	NTUA
Adding value to ongoing research that relate to the field of neuroscience and neurology, encouraging future or present university students to engage in research related to the ideas proposed in the PROJECT	Uppsala University
UE expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions, including exploiting added value to other,	University of Edinburgh

3 MES-COBRA D BUSINESS CASES FOR EXPLOITATION

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The MES-CoBraD business cases outline why the target market would be interested in the MES-CoBraD toolkit, what would be the benefit the market will gain from the results, and how the business models will create the bridge between the Consortium and the target audience, aiming at bringing the appropriate results to the market by the development of the MES-CoBraD business plan.

3.2 PLAN FOR EXPLOITING THE MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

Three phases will be implemented in order to realise the MES-CoBraD toolkit exploitation and sustainability potential. These are the following:

- › Business Model exploration,
- › Business Model experimentation,
- › Business Model implementation.

3.2.1 BUSINESS MODEL EXPLORATION

Business model exploration phase is aimed at generating value propositions, inspired by the matching of the MES-CoBraD outcomes to the unsatisfied market needs and gaps. These value propositions will be used as core components for the business models that will be developed in the next phase, namely “Business model experimentation”.

The aim of the Business model exploration phase is to identify the market trends, gaps and opportunities, and to produce a strategy for positioning the MES-CoBraD toolkit and the MES-CoBraD components in the market. It will begin towards the middle of the second-year project and an extensive market analysis will be conducted while considering the MES-CoBraD project outcomes. The main goal of the Business model exploration is to set the exploitation ground and thus challenge project partners to produce the project’s main market targets and value propositions. The main market targets of the MES-CoBraD platform are the clinicians, the medical researchers, the AI researchers, pharma and health tech industries, European Union and patients with CoBraD diseases. For all these markets, the state of play will be researched and presented to find the value proposition of its customer. More specifically, in this phase the key players will be identified, the market dynamics will be illustrated and the key performance indicators (KPIs) of the market will be discussed. These will be combined with KPIs of the MES-CoBraD Project to identify a most useful business model. The results of the business model exploration phase will be presented in the business model in the market analysis section.

3.2.2 BUSINESS MODEL EXPERIMENTATION

In the business model experimentation phase, the value proposition of its customer is suggested, identified and the preliminary business model is developed. During the project, a workshop took place, where partners discussed and defined alternative value propositions from the MES-CoBraD outcomes. The value propositions used in order to create the MES-CoBraD business model and also, validate the assumptions of the outcomes, their underlying logic and their purpose. In the workshop, its partner of the consortium had the opportunity to give its idea about the value propositions and then all the partners voted for the most applicable one.

3.2.2.1 Business modelling Workshop

The workshop was held on the 31st of January 2022 and aimed to activate all the partners in providing valuable feedback and their business ideas, considering their expertise and activities in our project. For

the purpose of our workshop, we used a specialised organisational platform, which enabled us to present the guidelines and the aim of the workshop along with a contained interactive environment for live collaboration under the guidance of Holistic. The participants identified the value propositions of the MES-CoBraD outcomes and drafted the Business model of the MES-CoBraD project. The partners voted the key points in order to create a business model canvas which incorporates the ideas and value propositions of the project.

Those value propositions are:

- › Deep phenotyping of CoBraD and their interrelations will significantly improve clinical care in people with CoBraD diseases.
- › Identification of impactful treatments or side effects of the CoBraD diseases.
- › Epidemiological insight for future (executive) decisions.
- › AI-assisted diagnosis.
- › Analysis of combinations of multiple datasets.
- › Clinical Decision Support Systems.
- › Secure and anonymised sharing of Real-World Data.

3.2.3 BUSINESS MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

Finally, the business model implementation phase builds upon the selected business models towards a formal business operation, which may include further collaboration plans of project partners. This phase also includes the finalisation of the IPR strategy of the MES-CoBraD Project.

The MES-CoBraD business and exploitation plan will not only provide details on the MES-CoBraD project partners but will also refer to post-project actions that may be taken by these partners at will.

Below is the summary of all the important and necessary actions that the consortium will undertake in order to have a solid Business, Exploitation and Sustainable plan for the MES-CoBraD platform:

- › Develop a market analysis,
- › Identify and describe the customer segments of the MES-CoBraD solution,
- › Identify, co-create, analyse and validate the MES-CoBraD business model,
- › Describe the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) involved in the MES-CoBraD project.
- › Based in the above steps, create the MES-CoBraD business plan and identify the key actors of the MES-CoBraD platform.

3.2.4 CUSTOMER SEGMENTS

MES-CoBraD business potential as identified during the workshop can directly split in three different stakeholder groups: (a) CoBraD Healthcare domain (clinicians, patients with CoBraD and their caregivers, pharma industries), (b) IoT industry (AI researchers and data scientists), (c) CoBraD researchers. Regulators/ Policymakers will be also engaged because they are the key stakeholders who influence the market, indirectly benefiting from the Project's results, albeit not as direct users of the MES-CoBraD Platform in most cases and (d) Media outlets will be informed of the latest research on CoBraD and will obtain a concrete framework to discuss labor social policies, such as the relationship between productivity and purchasing power or continuous workforce education, considering trained experts will need to constantly update their skillset in using advanced analytics tools.

3.2.4.1 CoBraD Healthcare Organisations

The need for a new top-down approach has emerged to enable clinical researchers to identify CoBraD patients from an early stage. So far, increased technological developments enable the early diagnoses of CoBraD diseases however tools for modelling the prediction of such diseases are lacking as well as the Real-World Data that need to be leveraged. At the same time, clinicians are missing said tools, so they are lacking behind in efficiently monitoring CoBraD patients as they do not have comprehensive and useful databases to keep track of them.

Thus, the MES-CoBraD platform will enable this process by being an open platform in which all the potential customers can identify and access real-world clinical and social data from patients and their caregivers through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast clinical protocols, leveraging scientific research in CoBraD and technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms of Artificial Intelligence, Advanced Analytics, and Expert Systems towards precision and personalised care. Naturally, the success of the MES-CoBraD platform is dependent also on the hospital staff's, and patients' and caregivers' willingness to change the way they use the systems that will improve their purpose and increase data privacy and integrity.

3.2.4.2 IoT Industry

Industry at the IoT and security sector are an important market actor of the MES-CoBraD Platform such as:

- › Industry producing digital wearables and IoT services, such as wrist-worn activity trackers incorporating heart rate and other physiologic biomarkers targeting consumers.
- › Industry producing communication devices and enabling devices, such as tablets and phones that collect consumer health info.
- › Cyber security providers, software development industry producing the applications that analyse Real-World Data.
- › Cyber security practitioners, experts in the security domain from software development industry.

3.2.4.3 Artificial Intelligence Researchers

AI researchers are another particularly important market actor of the MES-CoBraD platform because they can analyse RWD and give the customers of the Platform useful insights about the results of all the above tools, as well as provide the opportunity to patients and their caregivers to pursue a better quality of life, irrespective of their health and socioeconomic background.

3.2.4.4 Regulators/ Policymakers

Regulators and Policymakers in the Health sector are important lobbying actors because they can put pressure in decision-making procedures. Additionally, they help define long-term regulations to ensure stability in the market while setting the framework for business models to be aligned to relevant regulations.

The most crucial information for Regulators and Policymakers is how the market reacts to reliable simulations. The MES-CoBraD Project, through the application of technology on RWD, will be able to provide technical and financial information along with the health and social impact of that information.

MES-CoBraD will also investigate improvements and alternatives to current institutional and governance frameworks in order to improve healthcare awareness and stimulate the usage of the proposed solution aiming to empower the life of people with CoBraD.

3.2.5 MES-CoBRAD BUSINESS MODELS

The MES-CoBraD Consortium develops and validates the business model for the MES-CoBraD Platform. The business models will describe how an entity can create, deliver and capture value by taking advantage of the MES-CoBraD Platform. A preliminary business model has been drafted by the Consortium and the first version was finalised during the workshop. This business model (v1.0) that is presented in Figure 2 will function as a basis for the final business models that will be developed. The MES-CoBraD business models that will be developed will be the result of:

- › A thorough examination of the available business models/strategies for open-source platforms and their multiple variations.
- › A business modelling workshop that conducted in MES-CoBraD where all consortium partners were be present.
- › A thorough feedback that we will aim to receive from experts in the field where we will have the opportunity to pitch the MES-CoBraD business model. The core MES-CoBraD business model will be presented and validated during an event that will be organised by the MES-CoBraD Consortium.

Based on the identified business models, the MES-CoBraD business and exploitation plan will be developed. The preliminary MES-CoBraD business model is presented below using the Business Model Canvas¹ methodology:

MES-CoBraD Business Model Canvas		Designed for: MES-CoBraD	Designed by: HOLISTIC	Date: 31/01/2022	Version: 0.1
Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MES-CoBraD patients/ Caregivers - IT medical Researchers - EU and other public funding/ collaboration - AI open-source communities - Software and hardware Infrastructure provider(s) - Media - Clinicians - Scientists 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of Expert system algorithm • Improvement of the platform and tools • Disseminate the platform's research output • Keep up to date guidelines and clinical protocols • Continuous RWDData integration and Data infrastructure • Responsive to feedback from users • Good customer support, helpdesk, FAQ's Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intellectual Properties such as client databases, clinical trials & research data - Real-World Data sources and repositories - IT Infrastructure/ GPUs/ CPUs/Disk space - Human Resources such as Doctors, Patients, Caregivers, Stakeholders, Researchers 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deep phenotyping of CoBraD and their interrelations will significantly improve clinical care in people with CoBraD - Identification of impactful treatments or side effects - Epidemiological insight for future (executive) decisions - AI based diagnosis - Analysis of combinations of multiple datasets - Clinical Decision Support System-ES - Secure and anonymised sharing of the Real-World Data 	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producing research results • Data sharing between organisations/ Shared Analysis • Clinicians providing services to their patients • High quality research results for the AUT community. • Act as a repository of good practices for the medical community Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ MES-CoBraD Platform ✓ Social Media ✓ Newsletters ✓ Conferences & Lectures ✓ User manuals, tutorials, e-learning material, ✓ Educational activities to the public ✓ Scientific publications ✓ Existing customers- word of mouth 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinicians - Medical Researchers - AI Researchers - Pharma and Health Tech Industry - European Union - Patients with CoBraD - Media - Policymakers 	
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketing - Helpdesk costs - Administrative accounting - Engineering costs - Scientific Advisor cost - Database and platform upkeep costs - GPU/CPU 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ "Pay in Data" scenarios ✓ Subscription fees for use of Platform tools for researchers ✓ Platform fees for Clinicians performing diagnosis/ treatment ✓ Health Policy implementation grants ✓ Health Insurance companies-paying for anonymised data provision. 			

¹ <https://miro.com/templates/business-model-canvas/>

Figure 2: MES-CoBraD preliminary Business Model (v1.0)

Starting from the “Customers” for whom we are delivering the value (and would be willing to pay for the MES-CoBraD product), the consortium identified some types of customers: a) Public and Private Healthcare organizations (Clinicians, Health Networks), b) Researchers (AI, Medical Researchers), c) Software and Hardware Infrastructure Provider(s).

Moving to the “Value propositions” segment which is the value that we are delivering to our customers and the needs that we are satisfying, MES-CoBraD provides a) an intercorrelation between the deep phenotyping CoBraD and the people with CoBraD diseases, b) epidemiological insights for future decisions, c) AI based diagnosis, d) analysis of combinations of multiple datasets, etc.

The customer relationships as these are defined by the MES-CoBraD consortium are: a) Long-term, meaning that MES-CoBraD will interact with the customers on a recurring basis, b) Personal assistance meaning that the customer can communicate with MES-CoBraD after a purchase is complete (onsite, through email, call centres etc.), c) training sessions, workshops and pitch events that will be organised for the customers by MES-CoBraD.

Every business model requires Key Resources to run, thus in MES-CoBraD the consortium identified: a) IT infrastructure, b) Human resources for research, development and support, c) Human resources for marketing purposes.

The most important activities (key propositions) MES-CoBraD must do to make its business model work are: a) Further development and integration, b) continuous testing and validation, c) marketing and sales.

The partnerships and the network that will make the business model work are the following: a) MES-CoBraD consortium (mainly the developers of the components and the business experts willing to take up the results), b) Public and private healthcare organisations (Hospitals, clinicians, care centers), d) Medical / healthcare device providers, e) Certification authorities.

MES-CoBraD communicates with and reaches the customers to deliver the value proposition with the following ways: a) Online channels (website, social media), b) Conferences/Lectures, c) Newsletters, d) Existing customers- word of mouth, etc..

The key resources / activities which are most expensive (cost structure): The costs that are important to operate the MES-CoBraD business model are the following: a) Development and integration costs, b) Marketing and Sales costs, d) Infrastructure and GPU/CPU costs, e) database and platform upkeep costs, etc.

The revenue streams that represent the way MES-CoBraD will generate cash from the customers are the following: a) Subscription fees for use of Platform tool for Researchers, b) “Pay in Data” scenarios, c) Health insurance companies- paying for anonymized data provision.

3.3 PLAN FOR EXPLOITING THE MES-COBRA D COMPONENTS

The process of identifying potential business models for the individual components of the MES-CoBraD project has already started in the D1.2 ‘Scientific, Technical and Innovation Roadmap’ which was the innovation management phase of the project. The innovation management phase assisted the MES-CoBraD partners in eliciting insights for building potential business cases for their individual components. Towards this notion, webinars, workshops, Q&As meetings are foreseen where the exploitation and the innovation management team will guide the partners on identifying the value of their components in order to fulfil the project’s purpose. For the components that do have clear commercialisation potential, technical partners with the assistance of the exploitation team will build appropriate business models. The process of building a business case from individual components is the following:

1. Gather feedback from “D1.2 Scientific and Innovation Roadmap” and record the key points.
2. Exploitation options from all the discussions in the meetings that already took place during the project.
3. Bilateral discussions between the exploitation and innovation management team and the nine technical partners (NTUA, NIA, IR-HSCSP, SIMAVI, EVOLUTION) leading the development of the components.
4. For the partners interested in commercialising their outcomes, work on identifying appropriate business models.
5. The workshop that took place targeted to technical and scientific partners where the process of building a business model was explained.

4 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

4.1 CONTEXT

MES-CoBraD will develop a secure, privacy-respectful, modular platform that can be integrated with other platforms or be used as a standalone for using its independent analytics modules on the RWD stored in its secure MES-CoBraD Data Lake. The MES-CoBraD Platform and its associated components, evaluated in the course of four different pilot use cases will be available at TRL6 and will be possible to be commercially exploited after the project’s competition. More specifically, it is worth to mention that MES-CoBraD will not only deliver scientific and technical assets but also other important exploitable results, such as data and knowledge that can be further exploited in the form of business services: from consultancy, business analytics, customisation, update or development of new features in a service.

Overall, to achieve the long-term exploitation/sustainability goal, the MES-CoBraD Project and its proposed model will seek to become a reference tool in the field and framework for understanding the socio-economic impact of its results at European and international level. For this, it will have to meet the needs of the scientific communities and the stakeholders involved with policy demand for socio-economic impact assessment (funding agencies; policy makers and local, national, and regional authorities).

A critical condition for sustainability will be the willingness of the specific scientific community to continue to update the model beyond the life of the project. A vital role in this sustainability is the continuous interaction with the project’s experts’ group. We foresee several concrete options for the sustainability of the project after finalisation. The table below summarises the major exploitable items related to the MES-CoBraD research framework and data infrastructure solution along with the lead partners and main stakeholders involved.

Table 5: Exploitable Items related to the MES-CoBraD research framework and data infrastructure solution along with the main stakeholders

Exploitable Outcome	Targeted Stakeholders
MES-CoBraD Integrated Clinical Research Platform	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Pharma & Medical Informatics Industry, Policymakers, Health Providers.
MES-CoBraD research database	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisation, Pharma & Medical Informatics Industry, Policymakers, Citizen Scientists, Healthcare Organisations, and Health Insurance.
MES-CoBraD Services Stack	Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisation, Pharma & Medical Informatics Industry.
MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Modules (e.g., stand-alone Expert Systems Module, Data Analytics and Visualisation service, AI-based modules)	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Health Providers.
ETHAI model	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Health Providers.

Regarding the timeline, the MES-CoBraD Communication & Sustainability strategy is structured in three main phases as they are presented in the below figure.

Figure 3: MES-CoBraD Sustainability Plan

The first phase aims at agreeing upon the communication strategy and future activities of the project and creating the initial awareness in the markets related with the Project’s objectives and scope. The second phase aims at creating more ‘target awareness’ regarding the MES-CoBraD technologies with the key players and the potential users and informing the target market about the technological benefits of MES-CoBraD. Finally, the third phase aims at maximising the target market and industry awareness regarding the MES-CoBraD platform, thus contributing to ensure the project sustainability and full exploitation plan of the project.

4.2 METHODOLOGY

The MES-CoBraD Consortium will implement the Project with the vision to prepare the ground and reach sustainability goals. Partners of common organisation types will work collaboratively towards the different goals:

1. Pilot organisations maintain the MES-CoBraD Platform: All the appropriate IT organisations of the consortium will work collaboratively to develop the MES-CoBraD platform that will deliver to end-user partners. They will assess the platform in their replicated real environments, against targeted risks and threats including combined cyber and physical attacks. In parallel, end-user partners will also monitor and control the risks, threats and incidents in terms of reliability of the real-world data. In this way, end-user organisations will validate the platform and communicate the findings of the pilot operation of the services with the IT organisation to improve the MES-CoBraD platform initial deployment to prepare an outlook for its large-scale usability. As a result, by the end of the project the MES-CoBraD Platform will be assessed in replicated real environments but will not be ready to be installed and run at hospitals within daily routine operations. Further research and development will need to be conducted to increase its TRL level. In this respect, during the project progress, partners will agree on a partnership that will act to find the funding to continue the research work and pilot demonstration.
2. Verify the business potential of the MES-CoBraD platform: IT industry and all the partners will co-design with the exploitation manager the MES-CoBraD business models. To increase the business potential, they will take actions to present the business models at the targeted audience in order to receive feedback and verify that MES-CoBraD proposed approach meets their needs. In addition, MES-CoBraD consortium is aiming to get benefit of the strong demonstrations that will be implemented within the project timeframe, and present to the potential market the benefits of the MES-CoBraD platform and its components in replicated real environment conditions.
3. Further usage of the other exploitable outcomes: A rich property of scientific knowledge will be produced during the project implementation through the mature research that experienced partners will conduct in this innovative discipline of models with RWD in the health sector. Partners from universities and research centres will take the necessary actions to expand this knowledge to other

researchers and clinicians, progressing the field of CoBraD. In addition, evidenced based policy recommendations will be outlined from the pilot demonstrations. Partners from public authorities will communicate such information at EU and national level.

5 PARTNERS' INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLANS

5.1 CONSORTIUM MEMBERS' EXPLOITATION PLANS

A brief description of the consortium members' individual exploitation plans, as they were presented during the proposal phase follows below. During the project execution and since this is a living document, the members' exploitation plans may be updated accordingly.

5.1.1 NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (NTUA)

As a public institution of higher education NTUA is a non-profit organisation that will not perform commercial exploitation of the project's results. Nevertheless, NTUA will have significant benefits to reap from the project results that we outline below. The project's team will incorporate material and research results of the project in related courses in the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, perform seminars and further train undergraduate students as part of their final year projects. Postgraduate students attending the MSc in Techno-economic students will also benefit from similar inclusion of the project's results in courses, projects, and seminars. Additionally, PhD theses will be drawn out based either directly or indirectly from the project's results in the areas of NTUA's scientific contributions to the project, from members of the project's team, as well as new PhD candidates. These candidates along with the senior researchers and faculty members intend to further their expertise in the fields of cybersecurity in the health sector, cybersecurity in general, information security standardisation and implementation of standards. This expertise will be used to publish research papers, attend and present work in conferences, and allow the participation of NTUA in other closely or loosely related research projects.

5.1.2 NEUROLOGICAL INSTITUTE OF ATHENS (NIA)

The Neurological Institute of Athens will benefit through the MES- CoBraD Project since its goals are in line with the NIA mission of promoting brain health in Greece and worldwide. More specifically, clinically, the development of easy to administer and expert-based innovative multidisciplinary protocols through MES-CoBraD will help achieve precision diagnostics and personalise optimal treatments for people with CoBraD and their caregivers presenting at the NIA. In addition, the key concept of integrating novel technologies on RWD acquisition and analysis will significantly improve clinical assessment duration and minimise administrative processes, allowing NIA staff to focus on clinical activities and direct care to patients, while also minimising mistakes by improving data acquisition. Moreover, scientifically, the publication of novel research results will help promote the field of Neurology, and medicine in general, in understanding CoBraD, and will further establish the Sleep & Memory Centre and the Epilepsy Centre at the NIA as Centres of Excellence in Europe and internationally. Furthermore, educationally, the new information from the MES-CoBraD will be integrated into the NIA fellowship programs, providing both the best evidence in caring for patients with complex chronic conditions, and a first-hand experience in participating in multidisciplinary, multinational research projects that will be an asset in their future careers. Finally, this information will also be disseminated directly to educate the NIA patients and public within our regular outreach activities in the community.

5.1.3 FUNDACIÓ PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU (SP)

IR-HSCSP expects to benefit from the project in multiple dimensions, including: The SP will benefit of the MES-CoBraD project because its alignment with its goals to promoting care for the aging population in

Spain and Europe. First, the systematic evaluation of comorbidities in CoBraD will significantly improve clinical care in people with cognitive complaints and cognitive impairment. It will enable the identification of many subjects with co-occurring epilepsy and sleep disorders. Moreover, the implementation of the novel tools developed in this proposal will maximise the information to be gained from RWD data. It has the potential to save times and procedures or serve in decision trees that maximise efficiency of clinical resources in over-stretched memory clinics. Moreover, CoBraD will help us integrate our clinical and research efforts with the epilepsy and sleep units. The role of these comorbidities both as contributing factors to the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative disorders, but also as consequences are two of the hottest scientific topics in the field. Finally, CoBraD will also enable us to generate a European-wide cohort of patients.

5.1.4 VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL (VUB-LSTS)

The motivation of VUB-LSTS for the participation in the project is the intrinsic interest to promote privacy, data protection and security in the emerging innovative solutions and the keenness to identify and facilitate the mitigation of data protection threats and risks. Apart from the unique opportunity to enhance and adapt the EU data protection legal framework, VUB-LSTS will not only monitor legal compliance with the European legal framework but also will contribute to Privacy- and Security-by-Design solutions and upgrade its expertise.

5.1.5 UPPSALA UNIVERSITY (UU)

UU expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions. First, adding value to ongoing research that relate to the field of neuroscience and neurology. This may evolve into collaborations with other related European research initiatives and form bi-directional information exchange. Moreover, disseminating results and final knowledge gained from the MES- CoBraD, to academic partners, students, and the public. This may lead to further innovation and other research projects, as well as educational elements such as post-graduate/graduate seminars and courses. Finally, encouraging future or present university students to engage in research related to the ideas proposed in the project.

5.1.6 CLALIT HEALTH SERVICES- RABIN MEDICAL CENTER (CHS-RMC)

The CHS-RMC team expect to benefit from the actions proposed above in multiple dimensions, including the recruitment of dedicated research personnel such as research coordinator, neuropsychologist and PhD students. The solution proposed in the MES-CoBraD project will allow the CHS-RMC team to have a more dedicated time for research level clinical evaluations which in turn will increase expertise required for non-research clinical work. The CHS-RMC team expect to establish international research partnerships with leading institutions in Europe and brainstorm new concepts in dementia, epilepsy and sleep neuroscience for the advancement of public health. Finally, they expect to envision future innovations and research based on the MES-CoBraD project aiming at the advancement of a cure for neurodegenerative diseases.

5.1.7 KING'S COLLEGE LONDON (KCL)

King's College London expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions. More specifically, accumulating and diffusing the knowledge that emerges from the project to be further used for educational purposes (seminars, post/undergraduate courses, etc.) and for exchanging ideas with the

academic community. In addition, implement of acquired knowledge in designing more efficient, cost-effective and accurate diagnostic protocols for assessment of people with chronic brain disorders.

5.1.8 HOLISTIC

Holistic comes from a team of executives who have a long and extensive experience in the development of projects in these fields. They have the necessary expertise to undertake and execute complex projects of public, municipal, and private organisations of the EU. Holistic expects not only to enhance added-value provided by participating in the MES-CoBraD project but also to give feedback in the project's methodologies with the academic background in cutting-edge systems and technologies that the team leads. Holistic will provide a wide range of marketing and communication services that will be conducted during and within the project's life, improving its standing in the field. finally, HOLISTIC has at its disposal the required operational infrastructure to conduct the activities foreseen under the MES-CoBraD project proposal in terms of building and office equipment, as well as related software.

5.1.9 SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION (SIMAVI)

Benefiting of 25 years of expertise in the software industry, SIMAVI responds to the market needs in a dynamic and flexible manner, implementing solutions forecasted by the IT analysts. As the exploitation will be based on the concrete and real demands of the adequate professionals, markets and decision makers, the very new approach of the information system is the driving force to guarantee a professional and successful exploitation of the project results. The newly developed solution will strengthen SIMAVI's position on the ICT market and will allow the organisation to approach a new market niche. SIMAVI will exploit the knowledge gained in this R&D project by creating new business opportunities, enhancing SIMAVI software solutions and processes, by leveraging its knowledge to develop niches and specific software applications, which can be derived by the project technologies and methodologies, and contributing to intensive research excellence to Europe's competitive software systems and services.

5.1.10 LIBER

LIBER intends to benefit from the project by connecting project outputs to our network of over 450 research libraries from around Europe. Through involvement in the project, there will be numerous opportunities for engagement and knowledge sharing on data science, research data management, citizen science, and open publishing - areas vital to both the research libraries within LIBER's network and the MES-CoBraD project. In addition, LIBER will impact the project by applying its extensive knowledge in these fields. Over the course of the project, LIBER will assist partners with engagement opportunities for stakeholder groups identified within the proposal. This will ensure that varied and meaningful feedback loops are in place, allowing those who will benefit from the projects outputs the chance to be targeted, engaged, and provide their own input.

5.1.11 ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA S.P.A. (ENG)

As a global IT player in the digital transformation sector, ENG aims to deliver innovative solutions and strategic consultancy to several vertical markets. Between the most relevant ones, the Public Administration sector (also including the Healthcare segment) represents around 26% of the company revenue amount according to the 2018 Consolidated Accounts of the Engineering Group.

Through the Open Public Service Innovation laboratory, as R&D group involved in MES-CoBraD, ENG will

exploit the MES-CoBraD results mainly to improve its current offerings dedicated to Public Administrations, healthcare providers and citizens. MES-CoBraD project represents for ENG a relevant opportunity: (a) to further consolidate its expertise on the field of digital platform (by extending its asset Digital Enabler) and on the use of advanced data analytics, AI, and Machine Learning technologies in the context of healthcare services, as well as to (b) strengthen its capabilities of providing innovative services and consultancy to its customers in the health domain.

5.1.12 MICHPOULOS I. & CH. G.P. - TRADE NAME: EVOLUTION PROJECTS(EVOL)

The goal of exploitation in MES-CoBraD is to ensure the sustainability of the project's results beyond the project end and to demonstrate how MES-CoBraD has influenced the whole EU. Exploitation includes multiple forms. More specifically, Research & Development, by engaging new projects (EU-funded or sponsored by other sources), based on the experiences gained in the project, education, e.g., courses, at the university level or in continuing education, etc. Furthermore, community-building around the topics of the project, raising awareness for the addressed problems and the proposed solutions. Moreover, knowledge transfer, from academia to industry, by collaboration or via employees. Finally, contributions to Open-Source projects and standardisation, providing public access to the mix-net framework and encouraging its broad adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties.

5.1.13 UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH (UE)

UE expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions, including exploiting added value to other, ongoing research and innovation project in relevant domains with that of MES-CoBraD domain, as well as diffuse the knowledge that emerges from MES-CoBraD for the assessment, management and treatment of CoBraD to other health professionals and scientist to be further used for educational purposes, as well as for the advancement of its results through the experience of the academic community.

5.1.14 CYBERETHICS LAB. (CEL)

CEL expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions. More specifically, in the data protection and privacy framework: CEL will advance its knowledge on the application of the data protection and privacy framework to the democratisation and political participations fields and ICTs that will be reused to enhance its own current offering to public and private companies on GDPR compliance. Also, in ethics and philosophy issues will be identified and introduced in CEL assessment methods to enrich them, producing relevant results of interest to the academic community. All the acquired knowledge will be used to enhance communication and interaction capacity with health operators and patients' communities with the aim of improving CEL offering of services in the management of complex chronic conditions.